

Open Neo4j Desktop and create a new project:



Click the "Add" button and select "File". Select the dump in the selection window:



Move the cursor over the imported file and select "Open" -> "Create new DBMS from dump":



Choose a name and a new password for the DBMS and click “Create”:



The screenshot shows a form for creating a new Graph DBMS. It has three main sections: 'Name' with a text input field containing 'Graph DBMS'; 'Password' with a text input field containing 'password'; and 'Version' with a dropdown menu set to '5.24.0'. At the bottom right, there are three buttons: a grey 'Cancel' button with a close icon, and a blue 'Create' button with a checkmark icon.

Move the cursor over the created DMBS and click “Start”:



The screenshot shows a 'Project' view. At the top right is a '+ Add' button. Below it, a card represents the created Graph DBMS, labeled 'Graph DBMS 5.24.0'. To the right of the card are three buttons: a blue 'Start' button, a blue 'Open' button with a dropdown arrow, and a grey three-dot menu button.

Now you can explore the DMBS by clicking on “Open” next to “Start” and choose your preferred application.

For instance, you can open “Neo4j Browser” to explore the dataset using Cypher query language:



The screenshot shows the Graph DBMS interface. At the top, it says 'Graph DBMS 5.12.0' with an 'ACTIVE' status. To the right are 'Stop', 'Refresh', and 'Open' buttons. The 'Open' dropdown menu is open, showing a list of applications: 'Neo4j Browser' (highlighted with a red circle), 'Neo4j Bloom', 'Charts', 'Graph Data Scien...', 'Neo4j ETL Tool', and 'NeoDash'. Below the application list, there are 'system' and 'neo4j (default)' database entries, and 'Create database' and 'Refresh' buttons.



And you will see your new dashboard where you can create graphs and reports. For example, click on new report button, and then settings:



you can create a bar chart like this:



Using this simple query:

```
MATCH (v:Vulnerability)
WITH datetime(v.published_date) AS dateConverted, v
RETURN dateConverted.year AS Year, COUNT(v) AS VulnerabilityCount
ORDER BY Year
```

And by selecting type “Bar Chart” and clicking “Play” button:



Type

Bar Chart



Database

neo4j



```
1 MATCH (v:Vulnerability)
2 WITH datetime(v.published_date) AS dateConverted
3 RETURN dateConverted.year AS Year
4 ORDER BY Year
```

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